

Multiple ruptures on the North-Sofia fault at Gorni Bogrov from scarp profile and shallow geophysics

Alexander Radulov^{1,2}, Yordanka Donkova¹, Marlena Yaneva¹, Nikolay Nikolov¹

¹ Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 24, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria; e-mails: radulov@geology.bas.bg; dani@geology.bas.bg; marlena@geology.bas.bg; nik69o@abv.bg

² National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 3, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria

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Abstract. The seismic hazard assessment across the densely urbanized region in the Sofia Basin in Bulgaria can be improved through using fault data, in search of which we first aim to attain to a better knowledge on the past earthquake ground ruptures. Currently focused on the North-Sofia fault, we investigated whether, and how, the fluvial system responded to fault displacements at a site located near the village of Gorni Bogrov. At the studied site, a scarp delimits a distal alluvial fan on the upper surface from an alluvial plain on the lower surface. Although the scarp forms a complex structure that resembles a breached relay ramp, its fault origin is questionable, because the basin axial stream could have caused lateral erosion approaching the toe of the fan. The electrical resistivity profiles that we measured imply that recent deposits are associated with fault displacement. A fault located beneath the middle slope juxtaposes Neogene sand layers, covered by an alluvial fan in the footwall, with colluvial deposits laterally merged with deposits from the alluvial plain in the hangingwall. The scarp also contains a non-tectonic component related to lateral erosion affecting mainly the lower slope. Breaks on the scarp profile are interpreted to have originated through erosion repeatedly renewed due to multiple fault displacements in recent times. The interseismic intervals of the North-Sofia fault are inferred to be in order of thousands of years but not longer. The inferred interseismic intervals correspond approximately to those of the adjacent South-Ihtiman and distant Chirpan faults; however, they are noticeably shorter compared to the adjacent Zlatitsa and distant Krupnik faults. It seems likely that faults in a broad region on the Balkans release strain at remarkably different rates, independently from their proximity.

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INTRODUCTION

Historical seismicity, together with geological data, imply that the densely urbanized area of the Sofia Basin in Bulgaria is prone to large surface-rupturing earthquakes from local sources. However, the faults in the Sofia graben still remain barely identified. Data on recent fault ruptures are available from historical information and in early studies on tectonic

geomorphology. A fault is known to have ruptured the ground surface at the Vitosha Mountain front in the M6.5 1858 earthquake (Filaretov, 1858). Methodically sustained investigations reported young tectonic landforms related to ground ruptures (Guéorguiev, 1968a, b; Kanev, 1962, 1963). Decades after the early studies, we obtain new field data for tracing the North-Sofia fault. Supplementing the knowledge about the fault locality, along with the

history of ground ruptures, contributes to a valuable assessment of seismic hazard.

We refer the North Sofia-fault to the fault that bounds the graben from the north. The fault cannot be identified from the published maps, which show dense networks of cross-cutting lineaments (Ilieva and Yossifov, 1998; Shanov *et al.*, 1998; Paskaleva *et al.*, 2004). Fault traces, highly interpretive in nature, have been delineated along the Balkan range front (Alexiev *et al.*, 2016; Dimitrov and Nakov, 2021) or within the basinal area (Angelov *et al.*, 2010; Alexiev *et al.*, 2016). Our preliminary data from field observations suggest that the fault contains segments that bifurcate and overlap within the basinal area (Fig. 1a). The fault segments need additional investigations for more precise mapping. This fault could be the longest fault in the Sofia Basin, having an important role in the seismic hazard for the region.

In this study, we present data on the North-Sofia fault that were collected at a site located near the village of Gorni Bogrov. We measured a fault-scarp profile and implemented electrical resistivity tomography to image the shallow subsurface structure beneath the scarp. The joint use of geomorphology and geophysics is an effective approach that is widely applied to regions where fault traces are resolved with difficulty because of either low strain rate or artificially modified terrains (*e.g.*, Improta *et al.*, 2010; Štěpančíková *et al.*, 2011; Deckers *et*

al., 2018). A complementary but important task is to verify whether the site is appropriate for further investigations through paleoseismological trenching techniques.

GEOLOGICAL SETTINGS

The Sofia graben (Fig. 1a) represents the western-most extensional locus from a fault system formed at the Balkan range front (Bončev, 1927). The faults eastward from Sofia are associated with pronounced piedmont–range front junctions, as well as hanging-wall basins that have axial trunk streams. The Sofia Basin is the only sedimentary basin along the whole range front, in which the main factor for deposition and erosion is a regional river that transversely crosses the basin headed toward the Balkan range front, already since the Late Miocene (Kamenov and Kojumdgieva, 1983). The main stream is the Iskar River. This river has a huge catchment upstream from Sofia. The major volume of the basin fill near Sofia was deposited in the Iskar fluvial fan, including a fan delta that was embedded in the subaerial layers during Pontian and Dacian times (Kamenov and Kojumdgieva, 1983). The deposits that transitioned laterally from the Iskar fluvial fan to alluvial fans, and associated with smaller catchments from the surrounding mountains, were attributed to a variegated terrigenous unit, the Gnilyane and Lozenets

Fig. 1. Locality maps of the site at Gorni Bogrov with measured topographic and resistivity profiles (a). The scarp is arcuately bent and resembles a relay ramp consisting of two overstepping fault segments and a transverse breach. The map base on (b) is from a 1:5000 topographic map. The spacing of contour lines is 1 m.

formations, Late Miocene to Pliocene in age (Kamenov and Kojumdgieva, 1983; see also Fig. 2). Deposition in a lake environment (the Novi Iskar Formation) was partially coeval with the underlying (Gnilyane Formation) and overlying (Lozenets Formation) subaerial fans during the Pontian and the Dacian (Kamenov and Kojumdgieva, 1983; Yaneva *et al.*, 2002; Ognjanova-Rumenova *et al.*, 2008). The depositions of fluvial and alluvial fans were renewed during the Quaternary after a period of significant erosion. Pediments within the basinal area, along with channels deeply incised into the mountains, indicate that the erosion continued to prevail during the Quaternary.

The Sofia Basin is broadly interpreted to be a graben, in which tectonic subsidence facilitated deposition (*e.g.*, Kamenov and Kojumdgieva, 1983). The recent fault activity is demonstrated by local seismicity that has increased in the past centuries (Fig. 3). One large earthquake of uncertain magnitude occurred in 1450 AD. It was followed by five M6.1–6.5 earthquakes for the time period to 1858. The instrumental seismicity is relatively frequent, particularly when it is compared with the seismic quiescence at the Balkan range front to the east. Fault scarps are known in the SE basinal area (Kanev, 1962, 1963) as well as in the NE basin and adjacent mountain slopes (Guéorguiev, 1968b). Faults were suggested on geological cross-sections

Fig. 2. Stratigraphy of the Sofia Basin. Geologic Time Scale 2020 (GTS2020) from Raffi *et al.* (2020) and Gibbard and Head (2020); regional stages in the Dacian Basin from Andreescu *et al.* (2011, Pliocene) and Popov *et al.* (2006, Miocene); Sofia Basin lithostratigraphy after Kamenov and Kojumdgieva (1983).

Fig. 3. Seismicity and paleoseismological trenching sites from a region around the North-Sofia fault. Earthquakes of moment magnitude above 5.5 after Danciu *et al.* (2021).

based on drilling cores (Kamenov and Kojumdgieva, 1983; Shterev, 2004). These reliable data, however, are insufficient to trace the faults continuously along their strikes.

STUDIED SITE AND METHODS

Site description

The site was selected adjacently to the eastern axial stream of the Sofia Basin, to the south-west from the village of Gorni Bogrov (Fig. 1). The axial stream runs along the junction where the toe of the Iskar fluvial fan from the south merges with the distal periphery of the piedmont formed to the north. The studied scarp separates the alluvial plain from an elevated alluvial fan, which is fed from the north. The thickness of the alluvial fan is ~50 m (drilling core Elin Pelin 12 in Petrov, 2004), lessening to 1 m at the crest of the scarp according to what we observed in a quarry located near the profiles (Fig. 1b). On the quarry exposure, the Lozenets Formation underlies Quaternary alluvial deposits (Fig. 4). Fine-sand to gravelly sand layers dominate the alluvial deposits of the Lozenets Formation. The Quaternary deposits of unsorted cobbles, gravel, sand and silt have a matrix-supported debris-flow fabric. The development of a modern soil indicates that the alluvial fan on the upper surface has not been active in recent times.

The deposition on the lower surface at the site occurred at slow flow dynamics by mixing materials yielded from multiple sources. The terrain changes, traced from the topographic maps available for the period since the 19th century (de Livron, 1880, pp. 51–60), show that the depositional

Fig. 4. The Lozenets Formation covered by alluvial-fan deposits in a quarry, located to the south-west from Gorni Bogrov in the Sofia Basin.

environment varied from marshes to floodplains. The sediment was supplied by distributive streams on the Iskar fluvial fan, an axial stream, an alluvial fan from the northern piedmont and alluvial lobes and wash deposits when the distal alluvial fan was not active, as in the present day. Based on densely spaced boreholes, the thickness of the Quaternary deposits at the lower surface varies from 15 m to 100 m (Petrov, 2004). The relief on the top of the Pliocene deposits is evidently high, suggesting that the environment during the Late Pliocene–Early Quaternary was different from the Holocene, *i.e.*, the channels were deeply incised at the place of the modern alluvial plain.

The scarp at the site has a complex structural pattern. The segments are arranged in a bend that is convex toward the southwest (Fig. 1). The quarry was excavated on a segment that connects two segments in an overstepping configuration (Fig. 1b). This structure is interpreted to be a breached relay ramp. The scarp resembles a toe-cutting scarp (*sensu* Leeder and Mack, 2001), which may have formed through lateral erosion caused by the axial stream approaching the toe of the alluvial fan. Erosion during short-lasting flooding events could have contributed to the scarp morphologies or the scarp retreats.

Topographic profile

The topographic profile was compiled from the coordinates of the electrodes used in geophysical profiles. The coordinates were measured with a GR-3 antenna of the Topcon Company in real-time communications with the NAVITEQ Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) network using an IP-based connection. The uncertainties in the horizontal coordinates and elevation were ≤ 0.025 m and ≤ 0.039 m, respectively.

Electrical resistivity imaging

Two electrical resistivity profiles were measured. The data were acquired with an ABEM instrument Terrameter SAS 1000 combined with an electronic switching unit for selecting the electrodes for each measurement. The electrodes were arranged in a Wenner-Schlumberger array. The minimum separation between the electrodes in profile R1 was 5 m. Profile R2 was centered on the same line (Fig. 1b). A shorter distance of 2 m was applied on profile R2 to achieve a better resolution. The total number of electrodes was 61 in both profiles. The output current was fixed to 100 mA.

The direct current apparent resistivity was filtered for an error of above 2%. Afterward, the raw data were inverted through the software package Boundless Electrical Resistivity Tomography (BERT) v. 2 (Günther *et al.*, 2006; Rücker *et al.*, 2006). The computing meshes were constrained

with topography (Figs 5, 6). Inferred fault interfaces were used as additional constraints for further inversions of profile R2 (Fig. 6b). Low anisotropy factors between 0.1 and 0.3 were applied to support modeling with a good horizontal stratification, anticipated at this site.

Fig. 5. Resistivity profile R1 with stratigraphy and fault interpreted.

Fig. 6. Resistivity profile R2 inverted on a mesh constrained only with topography (a) and on a mesh in which inferred fault interfaces were included (b). Locality and interpreted stratigraphy are shown on Fig. 5.

RESULTS AND GEOLOGICAL INTERPRETATION

Resistivity profiles

Profile R1 images two distant lateral sections, both expressing simple stratifications that transition to more complicated patterns toward the profile center (Fig. 5). On the downthrown side, a higher-resistivity layer (generally 80–130 Ωm) covers a low-resistivity layer (25–40 Ωm , with a local decrease to ~ 10 Ωm). The abrupt resistivity drop in depth perhaps corresponds to underground water level. All layers are interpreted to consist largely of gravelly sand with subsidiary quantities of silt and clay. The horizontal layering that has transitioned to back-tilting at $x \approx 105$ m could mark the extent of the fault damage zone in the fault hangingwall.

On the upthrown side, the layering in the Lozenets Formation is smoothed by gradually decreasing resistivity from 540 Ωm in the shallow depth to 50 Ωm in greater depths. The horizontal stratification observed in the quarry (Fig. 4) cannot be resolved on the tomogram. The overlying Quaternary alluvial fan has a lower average resistivity of ~ 70 Ωm and expresses an abrupt transition at the base of the layer. Within the underlying Lozenets Formation, the resistivity decreases to 18 Ωm in a local zone at $x \approx 175$ m (Fig. 5). This local minimum in resistivity might be related to a hydraulic head elevated within the Neogene layers due to a fault acting as a barrier for the water circulation. We infer that the fault is located in the zone where the resistivity minimum within the Neogene layers abuts the back-tilted layers from the downthrown side.

Profile R2 images a distinct stratification in the fault hangingwall and a massive structure in the footwall (Fig. 6). Although profile R2 has a higher resolution, the stratigraphic boundary between the Quaternary alluvial deposits and the Lozenets Formation in the footwall remains very smooth. From this smoothness, we can suggest that the soil profile has developed for a long time, leveling the electrical properties in the two stratigraphic intervals. An alternative, and more preferable, interpretation is that the Quaternary deposits are very thin (< 1 m).

Identically to the interpretation of profile R1, the principal fault on profile R2 is inferred to juxtapose the local resistivity minimum within the Lozenets Formation and the well-stratified section of the Quaternary deposits from the downthrown side. The geometric complexity in the abutting zone might represent a principal fault at depth that has split into

two strands upward in the very shallow subsurface (Fig. 6b). A wedge-shaped region in the hangingwall, adjacent to the inferred fault, can be a sign of an antithetic fracture or flexure that approached the ground surface at $x \approx 135$ m. This antithetic planarity can be seen on profile R1 as well (Fig. 5).

Scarp morphology

The long-term fault displacements resulted in a cumulative fault scarp, which also includes a non-tectonic component because the fault is located beneath the middle slope instead of the lower slope (Fig. 7). Breaks along the scarp profile may be interpreted as a result of multiple displacements on the fault (Wallace, 1977). The breaks record erosion renewals after surface-rupturing earthquakes.

The maximum slope of 7° , obtained for a short segment at $x \approx 175$ m, defines an important turning point, downslope from which the profile comprises only concave curvatures, while convex curvatures characterize the upslope reach. The fault intersection with the ground surface, as it was detected on profile R2, is coincident with a concave break, which is interpreted to represent the base of the youngest scarp. The scarp height is 1.27 m. The crest of this small scarp is located 10 m upslope, at $x \approx 179$ m. Another break situated upslope from the small scarp marks the extent of an older erosion initiated after earlier fault displacement. The height of the cumulative scarp above the base of the youngest scarp is 8 m.

The region downslope from the fault to the base of the cumulative scarp is an area that experienced long-lasting colluvial deposition from scarp degradation. The height of this lower slope above the alluvial plain is 4.31 m. The relatively high fault position on the scarp slope suggests that the alluvial plain was incised through temporary lateral erosion, which was facilitated by the permanent tendency of the axial stream to downcut.

DISCUSSION

Interplay between erosion and tectonic subsidence

Axial stream in extensional tectonic regime causes substantial erosion, which removes the basin fill on a geological time scale (Weissmann *et al.*, 2015). Typical examples are the extensional basins adjacent to the Balkan range front eastward from the Sofia Basin. At the central Balkan range, the syn-

Fig. 7. Fault-scarp morphology combined with the resistivity images of profiles R1 (coarser resolution) and R2 (finer resolution in the center). The local slope is plotted on the upper panel. Two breaks on the middle slope are interpreted to represent the crest of the youngest fault scarp and erosional extent after an earlier surface-rupturing event. The cumulative scarp has a complex origin that combines fault displacements and lateral erosion temporary acting on the lower slope.

tectonic deposits have been reduced, at some places completely removed through erosion by trunk streams incised along the basin axes. In spite of the erosional potential of the axial stream at the studied site in the Sofia Basin, the significant thickness of the basin fill (Kamenov and Kojumdgieva, 1983; Petrov, 2004) suggests that the tectonic subsidence or increased main sediment yield in the Iskar channels has balanced the erosion to some extent. The erosion rate still exceeds the rate of tectonic subsidence because there is a non-tectonic component in the total scarp height ascertained at the Gorni Bogrov site. Furthermore, the deep incisions recorded on the boundary between the Lozenets Formation and the overlying deposits (Petrov, 2004) demonstrate a presence of stages in the basin development, in which the ratio between erosion rate and rate of tectonic subsidence was substantially higher than in Late Quaternary times. The primary reason for episodic occurrence of considerable erosion can be deposition that was reduced on the distal Iskar fan as a consequence of climatic factors. While the different orientations of the main streams relative to fault strikes and their catchment sizes could explain

the different preservation potentials in the basins adjacent to the Balkan range front, the statement that higher fault slip rates at the Sofia Basin favored the deposition since the Late Miocene remains a conjecture.

Implications for interseismic intervals

Paleoseismic data from Bulgaria show that the interseismic intervals of individual faults vary by one order of magnitude, from a few thousand years to more than ten thousand years. The Chirpan fault that ruptured the ground surface in the M6.8 1928 earthquake in Thrace (Bonchev and Bakalov, 1928) has an average recurrence interval of 2350 ± 643 years (Vanneste *et al.*, 2006). Three ground ruptures are recorded in the Holocene deposits from a trench excavated across the South-Ihtiman fault (Radulov *et al.*, 2015), which is located adjacently to the Sofia Basin (Fig. 3). However, the interseismic interval that preceded the M6.8 1904 Krupnik earthquake (Dineva *et al.*, 2002) lasted more than 11,234–11,888 years (95% confidence range), based on radiocarbon ages listed in Meyer

et al. (2007). Similarly to the Krupnik fault, the Zlatitsa fault has long interseismic intervals which are expressed by two earthquakes that ruptured the ground surface since 42 ka BP (Radulov *et al.*, 2022). Although the Zlatitsa and North-Sofia faults are adjacently located in the fault system that extends along the Balkan range front, the morphologies of their fault scarps are completely different (Bončev, 1927; Guéorguiev, 1968a).

The slow long-term slip rate of the Zlatitsa fault favored erosion on the fault hangingwall. Bedrock scarps are common, whereas scarps formed in young unconsolidated deposits were not observed (Radulov *et al.*, 2022). The fault scarp at Gorni Bogrov, by contrast, is located in the basinal area because the range front retreated in the earliest stages of basin development (Kamenov and Kojumdgieva, 1983). Moreover, the breaks on the scarp profile suggest that the interseismic intervals were sufficiently short to prevent the slope from being completely leveled. Therefore, we can infer that the multiple displacements recorded in the scarp profile have occurred since the Last Glacial Maximum terminated. If the assumption is true, the earthquakes on the North-Sofia fault most likely repeat in intervals that are more comparable with the Chirpan and South-Ihtiman faults than with the Krupnik and Zlatitsa faults. It would not be surprising if future paleoseismological studies reveal that the faults within a broad region, at least from the Pirin Mountains, through Thrace, to the Balkan Range, release strain at substantially different rates, which are indeed independent from the spacing in the fault population.

CONCLUSIONS

Electrical resistivity survey combined with an analysis of a scarp profile at Gorni Bogrov detected potential multiple surface ruptures on the North-Sofia fault with a precision that is appropriate for further studies through paleoseismological trenching techniques.

The interseismic intervals of large surface-rupturing earthquakes on the North-Sofia fault are more likely to be shorter in comparison with the adjacent Zlatitsa fault.

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Data availability

The resistivity and topographic data obtained from the Gorni Bogrov site in the Sofia Basin are available at <https://zenodo.org/record/8063545>.

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